

REVIEW ON MICROALGAE CULTIVATION AND HARVESTING TO BENEFIT THE HIGHEST ENERGY PRODUCTION

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ABSTRACT

There are many ways of cultivation and harvesting methods of microalgae, but there is never an answer of which is best to be implemented. Hence, this paper serves to solve the forementioned question on which cultivation and harvesting method could benefit the highest energy production. We obtained the results by reviewing various research articles and conducting numerous surveys. Thence, we discovered that photobioreactors and cross flow filtration are the best methods for cultivation and harvesting of microalgae. All in all, this finding could help in further studies of microalgae, which is the potential biofuel of the future.

Keywords: *biofuel; cultivation; harvesting; microalgae.*

1.0 Introduction

Algae are photosynthetic organisms that maintain photosynthetic pigments such as chlorophyll. They require true roots, stems and leaves characteristic of vascular plants. Most of them are aquatic, but they can also be found on moist soil, trees and rocks. Algae can tolerate a wide range of temperatures, salinities, and pH values (Khan et al., 2018). There are two major types of algae which are macroalgae (seaweed) and microalgae (chlorella). Microalgae are unicellular algal species that may live singly or in colonies. Unlike microalgae, macroalgae are multicellular algal species that can grow profusely at any time.

Microalgae can be a rich source of carbon compounds, contributing to various areas such as biofuels, health supplements, pharmaceuticals, and cosmetics. They also have purposes in wastewater treatment and atmospheric CO₂ mitigation. Photosynthetic microalgae offer a huge percentage of atmospheric oxygen (Randrianarison & Ashraf, 2017). Microalgae are powerful miniature plants that can be harnessed to produce feedstock for the industrial production of fuels and materials. Growth enhancement techniques and genetic engineering may improve their potential as a future source of renewable bioproducts.

In the past few decades, microalgae have been extensively studied since they can be considered raw materials for biodiesel production. This can reduce environmental pollution and fight climate change. This review focuses on different types of harvesting and cultivation of microalgae to see which will benefit the highest energy production. Thus, in this paper we illustrate which harvesting and cultivating method that achieve the highest energy production.

2.0 Cultivation

Algae can reproduce rapidly, faster than most plants. Autotrophic microalgae are cultivated using enriched CO₂ while heterotrophic microalgae are cultivated using sugar or starch. Microalgae are cultivated on land in open ponds or enclosed photobioreactors. Cultivation of algae requires light, CO₂, water and organic salts. Important parameters for algal growth are nutrients, pH, salinity, aeration and optimum temperature.

2.1 Open pond

Open pond cultivation systems consist of shallow raceways (0.15-0.45 m depth) constructed as concrete, clay, or plastic-lined ponds (Murthy, 2011). It is one of the simplest ways to cultivate microalgae on a large scale. Due to its relatively cheaper construction, maintenance and operation cost, open pond cultivation is widely used in the industry. Other advantages of using this system include simplistic operation and maintenance, low energy demand, and easy scale-up (Costa & Morais, 2013). Open pond use is limited to some types of microalgae that are adapted to extreme environmental conditions, such as high alkalinity, high nutrient concentrations and high salinity. Microalgae of the genera *Chlorella* are used for large-scale mono cultivation in an open pond because of these limiting characteristics (Costa et al., 2019).

The most commonly used and cheapest cultivation system for commercial production of microalgae is the open raceway pond (Acién et al., 2017). The open raceway ponds (channel length: 25 m; width: 2 m; total surface area: 100 m²; depth: 0.25 m) were provided with paddlewheels assuring mixing (flow speed at the water surface: 0.2 m s⁻¹). The pond was aligned with a PVC (or similar) liner during the construction of low-cost agricultural ponds. To ensure that CO₂ did not restrict algal growth, pure CO₂ was also bubbled in the system. The pond's working depth ranged within 0.1–0.5 m, with a base-case value of 0.25 m. (Béchet et al., 2018).

An open environment also poses other challenges for cultivation that contribute to lower biomass productivity than what can be achieved in closed systems. Evaporation of water can affect the concentrations of various compounds in solution, which can negatively impact algal growth. As temperatures fluctuate from day to night, the temperature of the medium can fluctuate as well. Biomass productivity drops off outside of the temperature range from 20 to 35 °C for most species used in large-scale culture. In addition, some cells will not receive optimal levels of light, while others may receive too much if the algal cells are not well mixed. Reported biomass productivities of various species in open ponds are from around 10 g/m²/day up to nearly 70 (Liang et al., 2015).

2.2 Photobioreactor

A photobioreactor (PBR) cultivation is a bioreactor system used to cultivate phototrophs like microalgae in an enclosed system with no direct material interaction between the culture and the environment. The photobioreactor can overcome several prevalent limitations in open pond culture design (Show et al., 2020). Firstly, PBRs minimize contamination and allow axenic algal cultivation of monocultures while offering better control over pH, temperature, light, CO₂ concentration, and more. Secondly, PBRs lead to less CO₂ loss while permitting higher cell concentrations and preventing water evaporation (Singh &

Sharma, 2020). There are three types of PBR which are tubular PBRs, flat panel PBRs and vertical column PBRs.

Tubular PBRs made up of long transparent tubes made of glass or transparent polymers stacked horizontally, vertically, helix-style, or tilted to optimize sunlight capture. A mechanical pump or an airlift device circulates the microalgae culture within the loop (Show et al., 2020). Large-scale tubular PBRs for the generation of *Chlorella* biomass have been built and operated in Germany and Israel in recent years. However, because of their high investment costs and energy requirements, these PBRs are currently only suitable for the production of high-value products for human nutrition, cosmetics, and pharmaceutical applications, fine chemicals, and industrial-scale inocula production, rather than low-value bio commodities, unless the investment cost and energy consumption for mixing are consistently reduced (Torzillo & Zittelli, 2015).

The flat panel reactor has a cuboidal shape made up of transparent materials such as glass, plexiglass, and polycarbonate, which allows for a short light path. It has an open gas disengagement system and a high surface area to volume ratio. Air bubbled from one side through a perforated tube or manually rotated by a motor to produce agitation (Singh & Sharma, 2020). High photosynthetic efficiencies can be achieved due to the large illumination surface area due to their high surface-to-volume ratio. Flat-panel PBRs are unsuitable for commercial-scale settings due to the numerous compartments and support materials required, the difficulty controlling culture temperature, and problems associated with hydrodynamic stress caused by aeration. This problem has never been reported in tubular reactors (Gupta et al., 2015).

Vertical column PBRs are made up of vertical tubing that is transparent to allow the penetration of light. The sparger, linked to the reactor's bottom, transforms the sparged gas into tiny bubbles. Sparging with a gas mixture ensures thorough mixing, CO₂ mass transfer, and the removal of O₂ generated during photosynthesis. Based on the manner of liquid flow, vertical tubular photobioreactors may be classified as bubble columns or airlift reactors (Singh & Sharma, 2020). An experiment has been carried out to study the algal biomass cultivation and lipid production of *Chlorella* using various PBR configurations. Results show that a bubbling column design is a better choice for the cultivation of *Chlorella*. The highest biomass concentration in the bubbling PBR was 0.78 g/L (Wong et al., 2016).

3.0 Harvesting

3.1 Cross flow filtration

Cross-flow filtration (CFF) is a membrane separation process that applies pressure on a fluid in contact with a ceramic or organic membrane known as the hydrodynamics technique. This technique is best for harvesting microalgae cells in large volumes and for larger particles than 1µm, namely, *Chlorella*, in which the mean size diameter of it is approximately 3.67µm (Nicolas-Julian Hilbold & Frederic Schab, 2013). In CFF, water flows tangentially across the membrane, thus keeping the cells in suspension, and the cake formed has a limited thickness (A.L. Ahmad et al., 2012).

Figure 1 shows the working process of CFF. The particles that are more prominent in size than the membrane pores are retained and referred to as the retentate. The smaller particles passing through the membrane with the liquid solution are referred to as permeate (Mariam Al hattab et al., 2015). The process of CFF occurs when the flow is applied tangentially across the membrane surface. As feed flows across the membrane surface, filtrate (permeate) passes through while concentrate (retentate) accumulates at the opposite end of the membrane. The tangential flow of the membrane creates a shearing effect on the surface of the membrane,

which in turn reduces fouling. The membranes used in this method can be either ultrafiltration or microporous. These membranes are available with a wide range of pore sizes and molecular weight retention. The ultrafiltration membranes have a pore size around 0.02-0.20 μm , while the microfiltration membranes have a pore size around 0.1-10 μm , resulting in the microfiltration being more suitable for *Chlorella* (Liam Brennan & Philip Owende, 2010). A cross filtration with a membrane pore size of 0.45 μm achieved a biomass recovery efficiency of 70-89% (B. Petrusovski et al., 1995). Meanwhile, the resistance of cross-flow microfiltration decreases as the cross-flow velocity (CFV) increases from 0.13 to 4m/s when harvesting (A.L. Ahmad et al., 2012). Despite the benefits from this membrane-based separation method, the major constraint is the significant decline in the permeate flux and the increase in the transmembrane pressure (TMP) during the process. This action affects the membrane to cause fouling due to the concentration of polarization layer development over the membrane surface, forming a cake layer and/or blocking the membrane pores (Sourav Mondal & Sirshendu De, 2010). Referring to the energy consumptions, using this method to harvest microalgae can range from 3kWh/m³ to 10kWh/m³ depends on the feed characteristics, system design, and pressure used (Michael K. Danquah et al., 2009, 73-78). The effects of hydrodynamic conditions showed that the permeate flux increased with increasing TMPs and CFVs (A.L. Ahmad et al., 2012).

Figure 1. Working process of CFF

3.2 Bio flocculation

Flocculation is a process where free-floating unicellular microalgae cells aggregate into a larger particle called floc. The surface charge of the cell is then removed by the addition of a flocculating agent (Muylaert et al., 2017). Flocculating agents can be grouped into two major types: chemical flocculants and bio-flocculants (Bracharz et al., 2018). The metal salts such as aluminum sulfate and iron chloride can remove 95% of the microalgae biomass at a standard condition. The main drawback of these harvesting techniques is that it requires expensive operational costs due to high energy dependence and is less environmentally friendly (Rinanti & Purwadi, 2018).

Bioflocculation is a technique where microalgae flocculate spontaneously or where flocculation is induced by the presence of other microorganisms such as fungi and bacteria (Muylaert et al., 2017). Flocculation using bacteria and fungi are alternatives to replace chemical flocculants, so the effects of chemical pollution on culture media can be reduced. The mechanisms responsible for this phenomenon are often not clearly understood (Rinanti & Purwadi, 2018). This method is more sustainable and cost-effective as no costs are involved for pre-treatment of the biomass for oil extraction and pre-treatment of the medium before it can be reused (Salim et al., 2010). However, the use of fungi and bacteria as flocculants requires additional special media as a source of energy for its growth. In addition bacteria and fungi can

contaminate microalgae (Rinanti & Purwadi, 2018).

4.0 Conclusion

In the final analysis of this review, photobioreactors seem to be better than open pond cultivation since it is more apparent to control the temperature, pH, and nutrient supply because of the closed system. PBR also has a lower contamination risk with easier mixing that improves mass transfer. The only drawback is that the installation cost is relatively high. Next, the advantages of open pond cultivation are the cheap cost and simple design. This results in easy maintenance and efficient cost operation. However, since the system is exposed to environmental changes, there is a high risk of contamination, and the temperature, pH, and nutrients are quite unmanageable. As for the harvesting technique, cross-flow microalgae filtration is advantageous over flocculation because it results in the complete removal of debris and microalgae cells. The equipment for cross-flow is also considered to be cheap because the costs are only associated with pumping and replacement of membranes. Furthermore, the structure and properties of the recovered microalgae are preserved when using this cross-flow filtration technique rather than the flocculation method, which approves the usage of fungi and bacteria as flocculants that can contribute to the contamination of microalgae. However, the downside of the cross-flow technique is that the large-scale recovery of algae cells can be limited due to fouling and frequent replacement of the membrane. Regardless, the advantages of using the cross-flow technique outcompete the flocculation to benefit the highest energy production.

References

- Acién, F. G., Molina, E., Reis, A., Torzillo, G., Zittelli, G. C., Sepúlveda, C. & Masojídek, J. 2017. Photobioreactors for the production of microalgae. In Fernandez, C. G. & Munoz, R. (eds.). *Microalgae-Based Biofuels and Bioproducts*, pp. 1-44. Woodhead Publishing.
- Ahmad, A. L., Yasin, M., Derek, C. J. C. & Lim, J. K. 2012. Crossflow microfiltration of microalgae biomass for biofuel production. *Desalination* 5: 65-70.
- Bracharz, F., Helmdach, D., Aschenbrenner, I., Funck, N., Wibberg, D., Winkler, A., Bohnen, F., Kalinowski, J., Mehlmer, N. & Brückl, T. B. 2018. *Harvest of the Oleaginous Microalgae Scenedesmus obtusiusculus by Flocculation from Culture Based on Natural Water Sources*. <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fbioe.2018.00200/full> [14 December 2021].
- Brennan, L. & Owende, P. 2010. Biofuels from microalgae—A review of technologies for production, processing, and extractions of biofuels and co-products. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* (14(2)): 557-577.
- Costa, J. A. V., Freitas, B. C. B., Santos, T. D., Mitchell, B. G. & Morais, M. G. 2019. Open pond systems for microalgal culture. In Pandey, A., Lee D. J., Chisti, Y. & Socco, C. R. *Biofuels from Algae* 1-22..
- Costa, J. A. V. & Morais, M. G. d. 2014. An Open pond system for microalgal cultivation. . In Pandey, A., Lee D. J., Chisti, Y. & Socco, C. R. *Biofuels from Algae*, pp. 1-22. Elsevier.
- Gupta, P. L., Lee, S.-M. & Choi, H.-J. 2015. A mini review: photobioreactors for large scale

- algal cultivation. *World Journal of Microbiology and Biotechnology* 31: 1409-1417.
- Khan, M. I., Shin, J. H. & Kim, J. D. 2018. The promising future of microalgae: current status, challenges, and optimization of a sustainable and renewable industry for biofuels, feed, and other products. *Microbial Cell Factories* 17(36): 1-21.
- Liang, Y., Kashdan, T., Sterner, C., Dombrowski, L., Petrick, I., Kroger, M. & Höfer, R. 2015. *Industrial Biorefineries & White Biotechnology*. Elsevier. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/book/9780444634535/industrial-biorefineries-and-white-biotechnology#book-info> [15 December 2021].
- Mariam, A., Abdel, G. & Amal, H. 2015. Microalgae Harvesting Methods for Industrial Production of Biodiesel: Critical Review and Comparative Analysis. *Journal of Fundamentals of Renewable Energy and Applications* 5: 1-26.
- Michael K. D., Brendan, G., Navid, M. & Gareth, M. F. 2009. Microalgal growth characteristics and subsequent influence on dewatering efficiency. *Chemical Engineering Journal* 73-78.
- Molina, G. E., Acien, F., Garcia, C. F. & Chisti, Y. 1999. Photobioreactors light regime, mass transfer, and scaleup. *Journal of Biotechnology Semantic Scholar* 70(1-3): 231-247.
- Murthy, G. S. 2011. Overview and Assessment of Algal Biofuels Production Technologies. *Biofuels* 415-437.
- Muylaert, K., Bastiaens, L., Vandamme, D., & Gouveia, L. 2017. Harvesting of microalgae: Overview of process options and their strengths and drawbacks. *Microalgae-Based Biofuels and Bioproducts* 113-132.
- Nicolas-Julian Hilbold, & Frederic Schab. 2013. Bio-based building blocks, case study of a large-scale manufacturing process. *Novasep* 31(6): 28-32.
- Rossignol, N., Vandanjon, L., Jaouen, P. & Quemeneur, F. 1999. Membrane technology for the continuous separation microalgae/culture medium: compared performances of cross-flow microfiltration and ultrafiltration. *Aquacultural Engineering* 191-208.
- Petrusevski, B., Boiler, G., Van Breemen, A. N. & Alaerts, G. J. 1995. Tangential flow filtration: A method to concentrate freshwater algae. *Water Research* 29: 1419-1424.
- Randrianarison, G. & Ashraf, M. A. 2017. Microalgae: a potential plant for energy production. *Geology, Ecology, and Landscapes* 1(2): 104-120.
- Rinanti, A. & Purwadi, R. 2018. Harvesting of freshwater microalgae biomass by *Scenedesmus* sp. as a bioflocculant. *The 4th International Seminar on Sustainable Urban Development* pp. 114-127.
- Salim, S., Bosma, R., Vermuë, M. H. & Wijffels, R. H. 2010. Harvesting of microalgae by bio-flocculation. *Journal of Applied Phycology* 23: 849-855.
- Show, P. L., Tan, J. S., Lee, S. Y., Chew, K. W., Lam, M. K., Lim, J. W. & Ho, S.-H. 2020. A review on microalgae cultivation and harvesting, and their biomass extraction processing using ionic liquids. *Bioengineered* 11(1): 116-129.
- Singh, R. N. & Sharma, S. 2020. Development of suitable photobioreactor for algae production – A review. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 16(4): 2347-2353.
- Sourav Mondal, & Sirshendu De. 2010. A fouling model for steady state crossflow membrane filtration considering sequential intermediate pore blocking and cake formation. *Separation and Purification Technology* 75(2): 222-228.
- Torzillo, G., & Zittelli, G. C. 2015. *Tubular Photobioreactors*. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/294287759_Tubular_Photobioreactors [10 December 2021].
- Uduman, N., Qi, Y., Danquah, M. K., Forde, G. M. & Hoadley, A. 2010. Dewatering of microalgal cultures: A major bottleneck to algae-based fuels. *Journal of Renewable and Sustainable Energy* 2:012701
- Wong, Y., Ho, K., Tsang, Y., Wang, L., & Yung, K. (2016, January 01). Cultivation of

Chlorella vulgaris in Column Photobioreactor for Biomass Production and Lipid Accumulation. *Water Environment Research* 88(1): 40-46.